

NEWSLETTER
ISSUE 1
NOVEMBER 2022

MAgnetically steerable wireless Nanodevices for the tarGeted delivery of therapeutic agents in any vascular rEgion of the body

Dear Reader,

Welcome to the ANGIE project's first newsletter!

In this issue, we introduce you to the ANGIE project. The central aim of the project is to a novel approach for treating strokes. By magnetically steering microrobots to the clot, we can deliver rtPA directly to the stroke site. This approach allows us to deliver higher concentrations of rtPA directly to the clot, while reducing the overall amount of rtPA used by a factor of 10.000.

In ANGIE we develop microrobots for targeted drug delivery treatment of conditions such as strokes.

We hope you enjoy reading our first newsletter!

Prof. Salvador Pané i Vidal
Project Coordinator

MAGnetically steerable wireless Nanodevices for the tarGeted delivery of therapeutic agents in any vascular rEgion of the body – ANGIE is an innovative EU-funded research project which aims to develop a novel, minimally invasive approach for treatment of strokes.

The four-year project started in January 2020 and involves partners from across Europe.

Team Members

ETH Zurich
University of Barcelona
Discovery Foundation
University of Crete
Experian Research and Consulting
University of Würzburg
MagnebotiX
Verhaert
SAFE

What does the ANGIE project do?

Most strokes occur when a blood vessel in the brain is occluded by a clot. This clot then prevents areas in the brain from being supplied with oxygen, resulting in the sudden death of brain tissue. Strokes are a leading cause of death and disability worldwide, and stroke cases are expected to rise in the coming years. The most common treatment for this kind of stroke involves injecting a thrombolytic drug (usually rtPA) into the blood, which then dissolves the clot.

Don't let their mini size fool you! Tiny mobile magnetic devices are showing huge potential for future biomedical applications. The EU-funded ANGIE project will forge ahead with small-scale robotics, magnetic navigation systems and localised targeted drug delivery. Specifically, the project will develop magnetically steerable wireless nanodevices for the targeted delivery of therapeutic agents via the body's vascular system. By creating a baseline of knowledge and skills for localised targeted drug delivery, the project will increase health professionals' capacity to treat multiple chronic diseases. Moreover, it will enable doctors to deliver drugs precisely where needed with minimal side effects.

<http://www.h2020-angie.eu>

www.linkedin.com/company/angie-h2020

[@angie_h2020](https://twitter.com/angie_h2020)

Recent academic publications

The papers are developed to help advance the current state of the art in the field of micro/nanorobots, and put forward our radically new technology which implies major progress in small-scale robotics, magnetic navigation systems, and localized targeted drug delivery. Also, to engage with relevant communities, policy makers, European organizations and citizens, and stakeholders to help us create an innovation ecosystem.

The ANGIE members published the following scientific articles:

- Salvador Pané, Pedro Wendel-Garcia, Yonca Belce, Xiang-Zhong Chen & Josep Puigmartí-Luis. Powering and Fabrication of Small-Scale Robotics Systems. *Curr Robot Rep* 2, 427– 440 (2021).
- Ntina G, Mavromanolaki E, Flouris AD. Toward More Inclusive Networks and Initiatives in Innovation Ecosystems: Protocol for a Systematic Review. *JMIR Res Protoc*. 2022;11(5):e34071
- Simone Gervasoni; Jonas Lussi; Silvia Viviani; Quentin Boehler; Nicole Ochsenbein; Ueli Moehrlen; Bradley J. Nelson. Magnetically Assisted Robotic Fetal Surgery for the Treatment of Spina Bifida. in *IEEE Transactions on Medical Robotics and Bionics*, 4(1), pp. 85-93, Feb. 2022.

Conferences and symposia

We have presented our finding in the following conferences, workshops, or symposia:

- Herrera-Restrepo, R. S., P. Martinez-Bulit, A. D. Flouris, M. Pinto, R. Moreira, E. Mavromanolaki, T. S. Mayor, S. Pané, J. Ignés, and J. Puigmartí-Luis. "In flow controlled synthesis of blood clots." *Public Health Toxicology* 1, no. Supplement (2021).
- Mavromanolaki, E., Ntina, G., Karatsali, S., Smarianaki, P., Pinto, M., Moreira, R., Pané, S., Mayor, T.S., Puigmartí, J. and Flouris, A.D., 2021. Evolution, gaps, and trends in the origins of innovation ecosystems. *Public Health Toxicology*, 1(Supplement).
- Meiners, K., Richter, M., Landers, F., Pané, S. and Lühmann, T., 2021. Marrying inorganics and biologics: Opportunities and challenges. *Public Health Toxicology*, 1(Supplement).
- Pané, S., J. Puigmartí, M. Pinto, E. Mavromanolaki, A. D. Flouris, T. S. Mayor, T. C. Lühmann, D. Sargent, and B. J. Nelson. "Magnetic small-scale robots: Principles, applications and challenges." *Public Health Toxicology* 1, no. Supplement (2021).
- Puigmartí-Luis, J., 2021. Microfluidic technologies for chemistry, materials science and biotechnology. *Public Health Toxicology*, 1(Supplement).
- Landers, F., C. J. Alcantara, J. Puigmartí-Luis, B. J. Nelson, and S. Pané. "Soft-hard magnetically driven microrobotic devices." *Public Health Toxicology* 1, no. Supplement (2021).
- D. Sivakumaran, F. C. Landers, Q. Boehler, C. Chautems, S. Pané, and B. J. Nelson. "In Vitro Navigation of a Magnetic Sphere using a Model Predictive Controller for Neurovascular Targeted Drug Delivery Applications", The Hamlyn Symposium on Medical Robotics 2022
- F.C. Landers and S. Pane. "3D interlocked metal-organic magnetic microrobots". MARSS International conference on Manipulation, automation and robotics at small scales (Toronto).

ANGIE Innovation Ecosystem

We create new market opportunities for entrepreneurs, companies and investors.

The ANGIE innovation ecosystem brings together health professionals, researchers, entrepreneurs and manufacturers providing them with online courses and technical workshops to understand the innovation aspects of the new technology and giving them examples of applications in different fields.

ANGIE Kick-start Programme

Let's innovate together!

We want to inspire and enable ambitious students, inspiring researchers, experienced professionals and talented entrepreneurs to start addressing important medical challenges today while our technology is still under development.

Thus, we created the ANGIE kick-start to support participants to develop their own idea for a targeted drug delivery intervention for treatment of a certain health condition. The programme consists of a series of workshops on targeted drug delivery and entrepreneurship topics. In addition, all participants will be mentored by an experienced venture builder, have access to leading experts in the field, and receive support to start a research project or a new venture.

ANGIE Kick – start Final Bootcamp

Present your idea for a new targeted drug delivery therapy

ANGIE Kick-start Final Bootcamp
11 May 2023 @ 1:00 pm - 4:00 pm CEST

- Receive individual feedback
- Get tailored advice for your project
- Check the technical and clinical feasibility of your idea
- Get invitation to participate in the ANGIE Acceleration Programme

In October 20, 2022 we held an info webinar on the ANGIE kick-start Programme. Participants learned about the ANGIE project and its approach to targeted drug delivery. Moreover, we explained what the kick-start programme is and how we can support them to get started with the technology platform.

the future of drug delivery

angie

Wireless nanodevices to deliver therapeutic agents in the vascular system.

Kick-start programme

Develop your targeted drug delivery idea

October 2022 to May 2023

Register now

Let's innovate together

h3020@angie.eu

Explanation / Example	TEAM 1 - Stroke	TEAM 2 - Dementia

In November 2022, we held the workshop "Discovering the clinical journey"

The Hamlyn Symposium

In June 2022, ANGIE project researcher Derick Sivakumaran participated in the 14th Hamlyn Symposium on Medical Robotics and gave a presentation entitled "In Vitro Navigation of a Magnetic Sphere using a Model Predictive Controller for Neurovascular Targeted Drug Delivery Applications".

MARSS 2022

In July 2022, Fabian Landers participated in the International Conference on Manipulation, Automation and Robotics at Small Scales which was held in Toronto, Canada. During a Special session on Micro/Nano-robots for drug and/or cell delivery he presented our latest results on 3D Interlocked Micromachines

Recent events

12th International Bionanotox Conference

In October 2021, we organized a satellite symposium during the 2021 Bionanotox conference to showcase our work up to that point as well as our plans for the future. The proceedings from this symposium have been included in a journal supplement published in Public Health Toxicology.

ANGIE Satellite Symposium

Friday, October 1st, 2021, Online
@ 16:30 - 18:30 | (UTC+02:00) Athens, Bucharest

ANGIE made six contributions to the annual BIONANOTOX conference in Crete. Unfortunately, due to the COVID-19 situation, the talks were held remotely.

Japanese-European Workshop on AI and Robotics

The Japanese-European Workshop on Moonshot program goal 3 "Co-evolving AI and Robots towards 2050" took place in Switzerland from September 21 to 23, 2022. A delegation from Japan consisting of 25 researchers attended the event in order to seek potential collaboration partners from Europe. We had some insightful talks and discussions about ongoing research and the 50 years ahead with some of the founders and current leaders of the field.

The delegation was accompanied by representatives from the Japan Science and Technology Agency JST and the Science & Technology Office Tokyo (STO), Embassy of Switzerland in Japan.

In November 2022, we held the online meeting Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery

Newsletter
Issue 1
November 2022

The ANGIE project aims to change the way we practice medicine. In this light, pressing questions around issues related to communication, ethics, law, policy, and education should be discussed before the newly developed technology will be released. In our last event experts from around the world explored different issues around targeted drug delivery in clinical environments.

In December 2022, we participated the Barts Research and Advanced Intervetional Neuroradiology Conference

Fabian Landers gave a presentation entitled "Medical Micro & Nanorobots: From the Lab to the Hospital" on BRAIN 2022

In December 2022, we organized a meetup event with medical experts

This ANGIE Meetup event pulled together medical experts in Cardiovascular and Cerebrovascular Diseases and focused on novel science, insights, tools and approaches for targeted drug delivery treatments

TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY FOR CARDIOVASCULAR AND CEREBROVASCULAR DISEASES
MEETUP EVENT

Our Awesome Speakers:

- Dr. Kostas Tsarouhas, MD, MSc, PhD, ERT Consultant of Cardiology University General Hospital of Larissa, Larissa, Greece**
"Atherosclerosis and coronary artery disease, thrombosis mechanisms and vulnerable atheromatic plaque"
- Dr. Michael Kiparakis, MD, Surgeon, University General Hospital of Heraklion in Greece**
"Coronary Disease and CABG"
- Dr Vasileios Siokas, MD, MSc, PhD, Laboratory of Neurogenetics, Department of Neurology, Uni-versity Hospital of Larissa, Faculty of Medicine, School of Health Sciences, University of Thessaly, Larissa, Greece**
"Future therapeutic options of transcranial magnetic stimulation in Neurology"
- Dr. Georgios Z. Papadakis, MD, MPH, PhD, Principal Researcher Hybrid Molecular Imaging Unit (HMIU), Foundation for Research & Technology Hellas (FORTH), Heraklion, Crete, Greece**
"Current status and future prospects of PET-imaging ap-plications in the management of patients with Gastro-Entero-Pancreatic Neuroendocrine tumors"

FOLLOW THE LINK BELOW TO JOIN VIA ZOOM

<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/83818358088?pwd=EkMlMFCR1RT2NkRWZDeWZaeTBPU09>

15 DECEMBER 2022
14:00 CET

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